

D5.5: EOSC Service Portfolio Roadmap

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Abstract:

This document lists high level service capabilities that should be part of the EOSC Service Portfolio offering. The input analysed was collected from the EOSCpilot Science Demonstrators, the early adopters of EOSC Services, and from EOSC engagement with ESFRI clusters and general EOSC stakeholders at events. A roadmap is proposed based on the findings.

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The deliverable is the second on service portfolio management topic. While previously the focus was on the description of existing services landscape and the actual process of IT service portfolio management, this document aims to describe the direction and reference points toward the implementation of the EOSC Service Portfolio Management¹.

An overview is given on the position of the portfolio management process in the EOSC framework, its scope, as well as an in-depth analysis of the foreseen steps of the implementation phase (chapter 2).

EOSC is an exercise for the benefit of researchers and research infrastructures and therefore must follow-up to and align with their requirements. The vastly different service management policies and practices in research environments, as well as the different discerned levels of quality by researchers using services, are recognised following extensive interactive meetings with representatives of different science communities. It was learned that foremost usability and stability are expected from EOSC, and community differences with respect to computing and data services must be taken into account in the implementation of services (chapter 3).

An even more detailed exchange with research took place during the work in the science demonstrators, one of the key experience exchange activities in EOSCpilot. Exercising actual workflows in the science demonstrator labs brought valuable information on services and the requirements on their prospective implementation. Also, it gave specific detail to the requirements broadly collected in the previous chapter (chapter 4).

Finally, the document presents a tentative scenario that takes into account the previously discussed macro and micro-differences in the scientific services spectrum and brings forward an orthogonal model for building the services portfolio roadmap in which EOSC deployment level and EOSC integration level are the entities that need to be mutually adjusted, depending on individual research domain (chapter 5).

¹ This deliverable follows certain typographic conventions outlined below:

Constant Width

is used for vocabulary defined in the EOSC Glossary. This convention is used on the first occurrence of the term for each chapter of the deliverable and written in title case style.

Italic

is used mostly for relevant text excerpts from referenced material.

1. INTRODUCTION

The European Commission (EC) launched the European Cloud Initiative² in 2016, to capitalize on the data revolution. The initiative aims to provide a world-class digital infrastructure that brings state-of-the-art computing and data storage capacity to European science, industry and public services.

The EC communication ‘European Cloud Initiative - Building a competitive data and knowledge economy in Europe’³ identifies “*five reasons why Europe is not yet fully tapping into the potential of data*”: 1) data is not always open; 2) lack of service interoperability to allow a multi-actor data consumption; 3) fragmentation of data infrastructures, access and governance models; 4) lack of a competitive High Performance Computing ecosystem to support big data processing; and 5) re-usability of data. The European Open Science Cloud⁴ (EOSC) is one of the solutions approved by EC to ensure Europe remains competitive in this digital economy.

The EC project EOSCpilot⁵ supports the first phase of EOSC. It focuses primarily on reducing fragmentation and improving interoperability between data infrastructures. The main focus of ‘Work Package 5 - Services’, responsible for the production of this deliverable ‘D5.5 - EOSC Service portfolio roadmap’, is to define a portfolio of EOSC Services upon which the Science Demonstrators will be built (as described in the EOSCpilot proposal). This WP aims to define the overall architecture for the EOSC and build a portfolio of services from existing research infrastructures and e-infrastructures.

The text of this deliverable relies on definitions defined in the EOSC glossary⁶, a work in progress by the EOSCpilot glossary working group. Definitions regarding service management terminology are based on the FitSM standards family⁷.

1.1. Deliverable in Context

The EOSCpilot project Description of Work describes this deliverable D5.5 as:

“EOSC Service Portfolio roadmap describes what services the future EOSC service portfolio should have, with input from known high-level user requirements, gaps from science demonstrators, user-driven service integrations and the resulting experiences.”

The EOSC Service Portfolio “*is an internal list of EOSC Services including those in preparation, live and discontinued*”, as defined in the EOSC glossary. The portfolio allows an organization to keep a record of all services during their lifetime: from the initial stages when a service is being developed, up to the final stages when a service is decommissioned. The portfolio will also enable the assessment and validation of the services across several common criteria, including technical (TRL) and policy (SLAs, Policy terms, etc.), as a prerequisite for their inclusion in the EOSC Service Catalogue⁸. The validated services can then be exposed to EOSC System Users via the EOSC Service Registry⁹. This deliverable (D5.5) focuses on describing high-level requirements for services the EOSC Service Portfolio should contain. The service requirements have emerged from the EOSCpilot Science Demonstrators, as well as from the engagement with diverse EOSC stakeholders at events. These high-level requirements and service gaps form a basis for proposing an EOSC service portfolio roadmap.

² <https://ec.europa.eu/digital-single-market/en/european-cloud-initiative>

³ <https://eur-lex.europa.eu/legal-content/en/TXT/?uri=CELEX:52016DC0178>

⁴ <https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/index.cfm?pg=open-science-cloud>

⁵ <https://www.eoscpilot.eu/>

⁶ The “EOSC Glossary” (<https://eoscpilot.eu/eosc-glossary>) by EOSCpilot Consortium is licensed under [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

⁷ “Part 0: Overview and vocabulary” (http://fitsm.itemo.org/wp-content/uploads/sites/3/2018/05/FitSM-0_Overview_and_vocabulary.pdf) by FitSM is licensed under [CC BY 4.0](https://creativecommons.org/licenses/by/4.0/)

⁸ In accordance with the EOSC glossary, the EOSC Service Catalogue is the “*list of all live EOSC Services that can be requested by EOSC System Users. It is a subset of the EOSC Service Portfolio and it populates the EOSC Service Registry.*”

⁹ In accordance with the EOSC glossary, the EOSC Service Registry is an “*EOSC Service providing EOSC System Users with a list of live / ready-to-use descriptions of EOSC Services offered by the EOSC System. The list includes (a subset of) the entries in the EOSC Service Catalogue as well as any other service worth being discoverable via the service instance.*”

1.2. Deliverable Contents

The remainder of the deliverable is organised as follows:

Chapter 2 summarises relevant work achieved in EOSCpilot project, as well as in other EOSC supporting projects. It builds a consistent view on the collective knowledge with a special focus on the EOSC Service Portfolio.

Chapter 3 analyses the input collected by EOSC representatives at different events, a joint effort of EOSCpilot and EOSC-hub projects.

Chapter 4 provides an analysis on the final reports produced by the EOSCpilot Science Demonstrators. Service requirements are highlighted and categorised.

And finally, Chapter 5 maps all of the findings regarding service needs to a service portfolio roadmap. It concludes the report by summarizing key points that should be taken in to consideration by EOSC supporting projects. It ensures a continuity between currently running and future EOSC projects, to benefit the most from the initial work done by the projects¹⁰ that have started to pave the way to realize the European Open Science Cloud EC vision.

¹⁰ <https://eosc-portal.eu/about/eosc-projects>

2. FROM COMMUNITY PORTFOLIO MANAGEMENT TO EOSC PORTFOLIO MANAGEMENT

This chapter aims to build on the relevant work developed by EOSCpilot WP5 about the EOSC Service Portfolio topic. At the same time, to frame the topic with the work achieved or in progress by other projects supporting EOSC.

The European services landscape is very much fragmented. The EOSC initiative intends to address this by bringing both the community services (mostly offered with limited to none sharing possibilities) and the core enabling services that support the EOSC System, to the EOSC Service Catalogue to make Open Science a reality.

2.1. Services landscape

In the previous deliverable ‘D5.2 - EOSC Service Portfolio’¹¹, we described the services landscape as being *“very heterogeneous in every imaginable aspect”*. The services are provided by multiple providers, and differ in purpose, technology, costs and funding mechanisms to the discipline / geographical remit of the services. This fragmentation is one of the reasons why Europe is not yet ready to provide researchers with an infrastructure environment able to reap all of the benefits from the data being generated and stored on a daily basis. Science is inherently diverse and continuously innovating. The adoption of agreed standards, guidelines and access policies will provide the necessary interoperability to address such fragmentation.

Noteworthy to mention, the existence of initiatives addressing the variety and complexity of Open Science, such as GO FAIR¹². GO (Global Open) FAIR is a ‘bottom up’ international approach initiative that aims at *“making fragmented and unlinked (research) data Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and thus Reusable (FAIR)”*.

2.2. EOSC Service Portfolio

The overall aim of EOSC is to provide researchers with fit-for-purpose services to facilitate and promote Open Science. These EOSC Services will be advertised to EOSC System Users via the recently launched EOSC Portal¹³. This portal *“is the universal access channel through which all European scientists will be able to access, use and reuse research outputs and data across disciplines”*.

In the context of EOSC, as well as a production-ready service catalogue listing services at a minimum TRL 8, the service portfolio will also contain a list of all services offered by EOSC Service Providers at some point in time. In full operation, it will capture those services under development (by allowing service providers to flag ‘pipeline’ or services soon to be offered as ‘coming soon’, and will also record discontinued services once offered within the EOSC. The service portfolio is not exposed directly to the EOSC End-users themselves as it is used as a management tool for EOSC Suppliers and EOSC System Managers.

As an organisation that is defining its business IT Service Management (ITSM) roadmap, one of the most important parts of the activity of EOSC includes the decision to set up a service catalog and portfolio. For EOSC, the broad landscape of service providers with different maturity levels, as mentioned in the previous deliverable D5.2, insinuates that many services cannot be immediately offered via the service catalogue before validation. This is a compelling reason for EOSC to put effort into creating a service portfolio. It also provides an historical perspective on where the federation has been, where it is now, and where it is heading in the future. The advantages of creating a catalogue are also relevant for the portfolio¹⁴, with the following extras: helps EOSC System Users interest in new technologies / platforms, while generating excitement across

¹¹ <https://eoscipilot.eu/content/d52-eosc-service-portfolio>

¹² <https://www.go-fair.org/>

¹³ <https://eosc-portal.eu/>

¹⁴ <https://www.beyond20.com/blog/how-to-build-an-it-service-portfolio-and-why-you-should/>

EOsc stakeholders for upcoming projects; it is vital that the whole portfolio (content and metadata) is well maintained.

2.3. The Context of Federated Service Portfolio Management

In general terms, developing a portfolio comes down to outlining the details around a few key areas, taking into consideration both service providers and customer (i.e. researchers) perspectives:

1. Capture the objectives of the service portfolio and create a plan that will realize them
2. Identify the customers and service providers
3. Define guidelines for interoperability and participation and policies to determine the service portfolio scope
4. Identify what services will be provided in the service portfolio
5. Build the service portfolio and a commonly agreed service description template
6. Gauging service providers acceptance of the portfolio
7. Deploying the portfolio
8. Using metrics for continual improvement

Most of these topical areas were not explicitly covered by the EOscpilot project, but rather by a concerted effort across the different EOsc supporting projects. Nonetheless, a few remarks are made for each one of above-mentioned steps, to better scope D5.5 relatively to its main goal - identify relevant services for inclusion in the portfolio.

During the planning phase (step 1), the first priority is to understand the customer requirements, and how the service providers' services are positioned to meet those requirements. The service portfolio management process will evolve or introduce services to meet demand. When it comes to publicising the services on offer in a consistent manner, one of the main tasks is to agree on which service descriptive attributes should be included in the service description. This work was started by the eInfraCentral project¹⁵ which produced a service description template¹⁶, that was initially made available to pre-agreed service providers to utilise in submitting descriptions of services based on a common, harmonised vocabulary, before making it available to a wider group of service providers to use. This template was further extended by EOsc-hub¹⁷ to capture additional information needed to validate the maturity of the service, and ensure it could be integrated into the service catalogue. The service description template should be further evaluated by other EOsc projects as they come into play.

In the second step (identify the customers and service providers), it is important that customer requirements and service providers should take an integral role in the creation of the portfolio. The EOsc System Users are a very large and distributed group. At the early stages of EOscpilot, a set of key customer focus groups, the Science Demonstrators, representing diverse science field domains, was identified. The intention was for these to function as high-profile pilots that integrate services and infrastructures to show the interoperability and its benefits in a number of scientific domains. In the process, the pilots were continually challenged about their service needs and/or to bring their own services to EOsc.

Regarding step 3 (identify services to be included in the portfolio), the progress of the science demonstrators was closely monitored, and their final reports provide relevant information about EOsc service gaps. The engagement of EOscpilot with communities at different levels, namely at interactive sessions at events, was explored to further collect service requirements. This topic is the core goal of this deliverable and will be addressed in the next two chapters.

¹⁵ <http://einfracentral.eu/>

¹⁶ <https://github.com/eInfraCentral/docs>

¹⁷ <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/>

Due to the federated nature of EOSC, building a centralised portfolio (step 4) is a challenging task. In deliverable D5.2, we reported on the multitude of IT Service Management (ITSM) methodologies for well-established projects and service providers. It is to be expected that the existing methodologies for service providers in their early stages of ITSM professionalisation, emphasize the diversity and thus the difficulty to federate IT service management processes, such as Service Portfolio Management. EOSCpilot deliverable 'D5.3 - EOSC Federated Service Management Framework'¹⁸ *“proposes a flexible approach allowing for various levels of service management maturity”* in order *“to organize and manage services within the future EOSC”*. EOSC-hub and eInfraCentral have been very active projects on the topic of producing their portfolio(s) / catalogue(s). The envisaged one-stop-shop for the EOSC System Users is gaining traction with the EOSC Portal, where the catalogue, as distilled from the portfolio, offers European scientists a single dashboard from which to access EOSC Services and to be able to use and reuse research outputs and datasets across disciplines. Nevertheless, to build a central services list requires well-defined ITSM processes to fully manage the lifecycle of a service. For example, EOSC-hub has produced deliverable 'D4.1 - Operational requirements for the services in the catalogue'¹⁹, which provides a recommendation on operational requirements for a service to be listed. Work is also underway on on-boarding strategies²⁰ to speed up service registration in the EOSC Service Catalogue.

With regards to step 5 (Gauging service providers acceptance of the portfolio), a clear and easy to understand service description is required, as mentioned in step 1. Well planned service descriptors need to be agreed between service providers and the IT Service Portfolio(s) managers, and gauged over time.

Steps 6 and 7, namely the portfolio deployment and ensuring the continual revision of the portfolio, are outside of the scope of EOSCpilot. Nonetheless, it should be noted that a service portfolio needs to be in continual renewal. Customer needs change over time, and thus the EOSC Services offer will have to be consistent with the developments and directions of IT usage in research. An agile EOSC IT service management should be considered that evolves and improves a minimum viable product gradually over time.

2.4. Service Portfolio Management and Federated Service Management Models

The management of the service portfolio is a central process for all organizations operating ITSM methodologies (such as FitSM). The goal of this process is to both define and maintain a service portfolio. The demands and requirements of the customers are taken into consideration while defining the specifications of new or improved services. In the end, this process ensures that the service provider is able to cope with current and future business plans.

With regards to how the EOSC Service Portfolio Management could be addressed from the service provider perspective, the set of recommendations made within EOSCpilot deliverable D5.3 on the federated service management models, can be considered. The proposed service management framework foresees *“various degrees of integration to the federating core”*, and three different scenarios were proposed:

- Scenario 1 - Service Promotion

*“Services are discoverable via the EOSC Portal/Service Catalogue, and are either offered singularly or as part of a larger, collaborative ‘bundle’ of services that are provisioned by one or more service providers. This goes **one step further than unfederated service provision by introducing a higher degree of policy-based human coordination between the service providers** [...] there could be agreements from service providers, or federations of service providers, to follow a minimal set of common processes and practices; those services would be deemed EOSC-compliant, albeit compliant with the Rules of Participation.”*

- Scenario 2 - Semi-Integrated Service Management

¹⁸ <https://eosc-pilot.eu/content/d53-eosc-federated-service-management-framework>

¹⁹ <https://www.eosc-hub.eu/deliverable/operational-requirements-services-catalogue-0>

²⁰ <https://wiki.eosc-hub.eu/display/EOSC/Service+Provider+Onboarding>

Similar with scenario 1, “where services can be offered singularly or as collaborative bundles, but in this scenario, **there are service management processes that are coordinated centrally, while some key processes (e.g. change management) remain controlled by the individual provider or its native federation.**”

- Scenario 3 - Fully-Integrated Service Management

“This scenario has **fully managed/controlled services**, where all service management processes are in scope and common to any provider offering a service and are documented and **managed as part of the EOSC SMS.**”

For services aiming at a low integration with EOSC described in scenario 1 (Service Promotion), compliance with the EOSC Rules of Participation²¹ for service providers, and an active management of the service description, are the minimum requirements proposed. These requirements will be validated and managed by the EOSC Service Level Management (SLM) process, responsible for maintaining the EOSC service catalogue. The EOSC Service Providers offering services in this scenario, will keep control of all/most ITSM processes, namely the service portfolio management (SPM). The service (e.g. see Figure 1, Service A) is built with external²² EOSC Service Components (SC 1, ..., SC n), and thus the service management is of the responsibility of the service provider, and it is considered ‘business as usual’. On-boarding procedures are being built by EOSC supporting projects, as mentioned previously in this chapter, to support service providers interested in making (some of) “their services discoverable through the EOSC”.

Figure 1 - Service Portfolio Management vs EOSC federated service integration models.

²¹ <https://eosc-portal.eu/governance/rules-participation>

²² <https://indico.egi.eu/indico/event/4330/session/0/contribution/4>. Based on the EOSC-hub document - ‘Service portfolio and service management and access provisioning’ - ‘internal’ services are all “supporting services that are needed to operate” the EOSC System. Whereas ‘external’ services is “the set of customer-facing services that are publicly offered” by the EOSC Service Catalogue.

Scenario 2 (Semi-integrated Service Management) concerns services characterised as aiming to integrate with EOsc internal core services (the enabling services that allow EOsc to operate). Most ITSM strategic service management processes (SLM & SPM) should/could be managed by EOsc centrally, while remaining processes are managed by the *Third-Party Service Provider*. Services in this scenario are typically composed of both EOsc external and internal services (see Figure 1, Service B, SC 1), with OLAs in place for all service component providers. A pipeline of maturity needs to be developed to be able to integrate the services to and to offer them in the EOsc Service Catalogue as integrated services that meet user demands. We recommend that all EOsc-dependent service components remain managed by EOsc SPM for evaluation and promotion to the service catalogue, whereas the EOsc external service components agree on the Rules of Participation with the EOsc SLM process.

For services aiming for a tighter integration (scenario 3; e.g. EOsc enabling/internal services such as AAI, and co-dependent service components), the requirements will be higher, namely compliance with all EOsc service management processes. Thus, the SPM (and SLM) processes will be managed as part of the EOsc Service Management System, as indicated in Figure 1 (Service C), and not by the service provider. It is likely that the component services when offered as fully integrated services will fall into the scope of the EOsc SPM processes.

Based on the work performed by EOscpilot T5.2 and our collective knowledge on the topic while collaborating with the EOsc supporting projects, it is possible to make general recommendations to define and thereby scope the service portfolio and its management in the context of EOsc, namely:

1. The EOsc Service Portfolio will comprise only EOsc Services for which EOsc is wholly responsible (the internal services);
2. The scope of EOsc Service Portfolio Management will be confined to the services in the EOsc Service Portfolio;
3. Service providers should not lose responsibility for managing their own service portfolio for services not under the responsibility of the EOsc (the external services);
4. The integration of external services in the EOsc Service Catalogue should be handled through procedures defined inside the service level management process. These procedures should be aligned with the procedure(s) for the integration of internal services from the EOsc Service Portfolio into the EOsc Service Catalogue.
5. The service portfolio of EOsc must be user driven to results in a balanced combination of general IT services (e.g. compute, storage and data management services) and thematic research directed IT services (e.g. scientific applications, data analytics and modeling tools etc.) that cater for scientific disciplines directly.
6. The service portfolio of EOsc must be user driven to results in a balanced combination of general IT services (e.g. compute, storage and data management services) and thematic research directed IT services (e.g. scientific applications, data analytics and modeling tools etc.) that cater for scientific disciplines directly.

A service portfolio is subject to continuous improvement and maintenance therefore, it develops over time. The EOsc Service Portfolio Management is a strategic ITSM process with high impact for all EOsc stakeholders. This process drives the development of the EOsc Service Portfolio and ensures EOsc is able to meet the demands and requirements from its customers. As such, we recommend that the *EOsc Governance* body maintains control of this process to ensure current and future business plans succeed.

3. OBSERVATIONS REGARDING EOsc ENGAGEMENT EVENTS

3.1. Background and objective

The EOsc is taking shape by federating generic and thematic services into a single integrated service portfolio. Since their start in 2017 & 2018, the EOscpilot, eInfraCentral and EOsc-hub projects, respectively, progressed in establishing:

1. an initial service portfolio with services offered from various e-infrastructure and Research Infrastructure and scientific providers;
2. a service management framework that helps new providers join and operate at high quality;
3. tools and services that can be used by service providers to expand their service capabilities;
4. processes and policies that help providers align their offerings in the broader landscape.

The developments in the early stages of EOsc should be continuously updated with the expectations of the stakeholders and with the actual state of the required and offered services by the research infrastructures (RI) and resource providers. To start this iterative process, dedicated interactive sessions, outlined below, were held with representatives of the EOsc supporting projects, current and prospective researchers, research infrastructures and infrastructure providers, in which service provisioning, concrete services and expectations of services to be provided by EOsc were discussed.

This chapter contains the results from four interactive workshops with EOsc stakeholders. The outcome helped to draw a more detailed picture of the services prospective EOsc System Users would need in EOsc.

3.2. Meetings with stakeholders

3.2.1. Sessions and format

The project sought interaction with communities by attending two European Strategy Forum on Research (ESFRI) cluster project meetings, namely ASTERICS²³ and ENVRIplus²⁴. These projects coordinate RIs in the fields of astronomy / astro(particle) physics and environmental / earth sciences respectively. The engagement of EOscpilot with EOsc stakeholders continued in other big events, namely the Digital Infrastructures for Research (DI4R)²⁵ and the EOsc Stakeholders Forum²⁶. The project organised in total four sessions at the following events:

- Digital Infrastructures for Research 2018 (Lisbon, 9-11 Oct. 2018)²⁷
- 3rd ASTERICS-OBELICS workshop (Cambridge, 23-26 Oct. 2018)²⁸
- 7th ENVRI week (Latvia, 5-9 Nov. 2018)²⁹
- 2nd EOsc stakeholders forum (Vienna, 21-22 Nov. 2018)³⁰

The sessions at the ASTERICS-OBELICS workshop and at DI4R conference were prepared in cooperation with members of the EOsc-hub and eInfraCentral projects. EOsc-hub deliverable 'D2.6 - First Service roadmap, service portfolio and service catalogue' (under review) has some similar goals than EOscpilot D5.5, which explains the close engagement between the two projects.

²³ <https://www.asterics2020.eu/>

²⁴ <http://www.envriplus.eu/>

²⁵ <https://www.digitalinfrastructures.eu/>

²⁶ <https://eoscipilot.eu/events/second-eosc-stakeholders-forum>

²⁷ <https://indico.egi.eu/indico/event/3973/program>

²⁸ <https://www.asterics2020.eu/event/third-asterics-obelics-workshop>

²⁹ <http://www.envriplus.eu/2018/10/23/registration-to-7th-envri-week-in-riga-is-now-opened/>

³⁰ <https://eoscipilot.eu/events/second-eosc-stakeholders-forum>

The sessions at the ASTERICS-OBELICS, ENVRIplus and DI4R events, were organized in a World Cafe³¹ similar style format. The goal of this session format was to take advantage of the collective knowledge of the audience (see Annex A, Table 1) to extract high-level needs for services and identify priorities for the coming years to develop a service roadmap. The approach was, after setting the context, to create small discussion groups with moderators and ask specific questions (see Annex A, Table 2). At the end of the discussion phase, outputs per group were collected, summarized and used later as inputs to the service road-mapping activities of EOsc. The discussions were kept alive by using interactive presentation tooling³², where the accumulated results were shown live for all of the audience.

The workshop at the EOscpilot stakeholder forum had the format of a panel discussion. The panelists introduced themselves shortly and responded to a set of prepared questions. The audience took part in the discussions that followed, and were able to submit feedback live to the panel and audience via online tooling.

3.2.2. Selection of responses, uptake from discussion

The collected material from the discussion was foremost a large list of free format answers to the various questions posed. This material was subsequently ordered, grouped and aligned to similar answers. The editing and selection process followed an iterative approach where the raw material was repeatedly scanned and answers were sorted into common groups.

A few responses and discussion topics have been filtered out. The authors of this report have not taken them into consideration, not because they are irrelevant, but rather they are the result of lack of information/expectations about the EOsc, or because the answer(s) are not directly relevant for the main goal of this deliverable: identify high-level service requirements to build a service portfolio roadmap. For example, it may not be known by an individual researcher that a community is already involved in demonstrating usage of EOsc services or, as another example, the recommendation that services must be easily usable although no indication of easiness is provided.

3.3. Responses and outcome of the sessions

As mentioned, the outcome collected from the four interactive sessions EOscpilot participated was grouped into common groups. The theme of each grouping emerged on an ad hoc basis, after several iterations of the raw answers provided by the participants. We defined the following thematic groups:

- On quality and ease of access to EOsc service offerings.
- Prospective services and service developments.
- Short-term community needs the EOsc should address.
- Services and uptakes that developers and IT aware researchers like to see in EOsc.

The scope for each group is described in the next pages, along with a summary list of participants feedback that fit the theme. This summary represents an unsorted and not-necessarily interrelated wish list by (potential) EOsc users. Furthermore, this list is generated from limited statistics and may be subject to some intrinsic biases that we did not explore.

3.3.1. On quality and ease of access to EOsc service offerings

Participants of the sessions responded with many aspects on the quality and usability of services. Their experiences with existing services are projected into what they would expect to have in EOsc. Answers fit the categories transparency, convenience, usability and accountability. These qualities have a loose relationship to FAIR criteria which nowadays seem to be applied to services. Trustworthiness of services is for that matter in the same category. Together, they form the basis for trusted service offerings, which will be a very important selling point of the EOsc. By no means are these categories meant to be an exhaustive

³¹ <http://www.theworldcafe.com/>

³² <https://www.mentimeter.com/>

listing to define the quality of a service but they are a good start especially from the perspective of the users of the services.

Transparency

- Provide a searchable service catalogue with descriptions and other relevant information (e.g. SLA).
- The ratio of usage costs and quality of services must be balanced. The acceptance depends on the community and the type of service.
- Origin and provider of services must be communicated transparently and must be verifiable.
- Data services must be more than bare bones resource provisioning. Each data service has to deliver added-value to the data management cycle.
- Clear explanations of the service capability as well as its intended use and designated community.

Convenience

- Data services must be delivered with competence and competent support, e.g. assisting how to use the services to improve provenance or FAIRness.
- Mediating access to data. Data services may be offered through a wizard that helps the user to select the best possible tool or method provided by the service.
- Access to services via single sign-on, which gives the possibility to track the user who added or manipulated the data thus ensuring provenance.
- Services must be available 24/7 since research is done in the same time window. Service downtimes should thus be minimised.

Usability

- Data services must offer a high level of integration. Tools for visualisation, annotation, manipulation and analysis need to work in synchronisation. Orchestration could be done via a virtual dashboard. This also will enhance standardisation and bridge services developed in different communities.
- Data services should include central registries that give in depth information of the data (e.g. where was the data measured, what ontologies are being used, what collections exist, what vocabulary is used). Services should exist that make finding data easier.
- Communities need to be given a central overview on how to properly provide metadata to prevent data fragmentation.
- Provide consolidated or common access to commercial (cloud) providers e.g. for redundancy.
- Interoperability of data services of existing infrastructures and alignment with existing procedures and workflows.

Accountability and trust

- Use of EOsc services must be accountable, e.g. tracking library access for usage statistics.
- Users must be able to monitor services they are using.
- Services as well as the data must have some verifiable quality check, or the origins must be accountable.
- Efficient, simplified contracting and timely legal agreements.
- Proven sustainability and long-time service offering.
- Ensure and prove that data is properly protected and regulated.

3.3.2. Prospective services and services development

Participants were asked about their expectations if services they currently operate would enter the EOOSC ecosystem. Would EOOSC be a good place to host existing and future services although it is clear that some autonomy will be lost? What capabilities must be present in order to effectively support the research workflow in existence today and what premises must be fulfilled to relieve current limitations and bottlenecks?

In general, the audience sees a good number of benefits if services are offered by EOOSC, but they also hint at possible limitations that must be taken into account. Users will only use EOOSC if it is reliable and offers the content which is promised. Participating in EOOSC ideally should show direct user benefit, added-value and return of effort, and EOOSC should be seen as your partner in science!

Data management benefits and limitations

- Identity and authentication across systems and a universally adopted AAI. A single user identity in the EOOSC would be beneficial in data management because it gives the possibility to track the user who added or manipulated the data thus ensuring provenance.
- Balance expectations and offerings and never sell 'fake' services.
- Integration of services in EOOSC must improve interoperability and reduce the number of similar service offerings within the community. A reduction of the number of services could reduce fragmentation and help harmonise data and data practices. Also, it will give access to data otherwise hidden or unknown.
- Repositories and parts of the data workflows can be run at a single location except for archives; they need duplicates.
- Domain specific services should only be integrated in EOOSC if their domain specific properties can be guaranteed or even improved.
- Services should honor the fact that different data formats exist and provide guidance to researchers when accessing data sources.
- Enable cross domain data access.

Operational benefits

- EOOSC should offer an incubator area where services are exposed in early development stage.
- The larger span over Europe and the greater number of participants in EOOSC could be used to assist in building communities and collaborations for developers of software, drivers of open science, improve standardisation and facilitate in cross domain development and research.
- Similarly, the requests and expectations for training services and training material can be more easily addressed in a larger framework with a consolidated service offering.
- Enable and showcase cross-domain interoperability/collaboration and mediate community partnerships.
- Standardisation can gain momentum in a consolidated service space with all actors on board.
- Uptake in EOOSC results in promotion of services. This will attract other domains/communities and will benefit communities that work global.

3.3.3. Short-term community needs the EOOSC should address

Some of the services mentioned during the discussions were said to be lacking and currently restricting scientific workflows. These services are in the top wish list and we suggest that EOOSC should address them as soon as possible, namely:

- Single sign-on and common AAI.
- Long-term storage that is trusted and secure.
- Integration of data originating from different sources.
- Tools for discovery and contextualisation of existing data.
- Workflow composition and workflow deployment over different computer centers.
- Make EOSC services stable and sustainable.
- Services that can automatically access/retrieve data referenced with PIDs.
- Solutions that provide storage near computing (and vice versa).
- Transparent and low threshold routes for granting access to EOSC services that enable and unlock scientific compute services across borders.

3.3.4. Other needs from developers and IT aware researchers

Sometimes, not directly related to the discussion point at hand, participants made a clear stance regarding necessary services that a future EOSC should operate in order to increase acceptance of the EOSC as a whole by the community. This collection of requests is kept in this document for the record since it is felt that the information is relevant but may have been addressed already in other activities in EOSCPilot or other projects. Nevertheless, the list can be checked at a later date and used to extract further service enhancements or developments:

- Services for easily moving large amounts of data.
- Services to manage large distributed data storage.
- Services for long-term data storage.
- Normalised framework and common semantics for use of PIDs.
- A repository for software.
- Services/tools for data compression.
- Services/tools and means to setup tailor-made networking and network on demand.
- Services/tools that make searching for data easy.
- Services/tools to trawl, improve, reuse metadata, annotations and to support provenance.

3.4. Conclusions

Large research programs, such as the ESFRI projects, often have highly technical, complex and dedicated data storage and analysis requirements. This appears to be intrinsic to the data gathering and subsequent analysis. To cater to these programs requires dedicated resources (human resources and hardware) for EOSC to align with these important key science projects from an early stage and onwards.

At DI4R and the EOSC Stakeholders Forum, the participants had a very heterogeneous role, and associated to diverse research fields, from large communities (e.g. ESFRI projects, CERN) to the long tail of science groups. The interest in possibilities for data exchange and standardisation differs per community, signaling the multitude of different requirements and options that live in the research community and which EOSC should equally address.

Overall, the single most commonly referred feature was the ability to use services using **single sign-on** based on an underlying common AAI framework. This request made it in all top wish lists compiled during the sessions and was repeatedly mentioned. Other commonly referred requests were the **inability to share data**, the **need to gain access to remote data** and the requirement for **stable and sustained services**.

4. OBSERVATIONS REGARDING THE SCIENCE DEMONSTRATORS

4.1. Background and objective

This chapter seeks to respond to the high-level requirements and gaps identified during the design and operation of the EOscpilot Science Demonstrators performed under Work Package 4. The aim of the Science Demonstrators is *“to show the relevance and usefulness of the EOsc Services and their enabling of data reuse, to drive the EOsc development”*, and in doing so a number of observations were made concerning opportunities and gaps. The fifteen Science Demonstrators published final reports during the course of November/December 2018, following on from their more detailed reporting during the duration of their tasks. Deliverable ‘D4.4 - Consolidated Science Demonstrator evaluation report’³³ describes the methodology followed and “presents an evaluation of the findings, feedback, lessons learnt and recommendations of the Science Demonstrators as representative groups of customers of future EOsc services.” Furthermore, “their input will be used to drive and prioritise the integration of the candidate EOsc services”.

The reports of the Science Demonstrators present an opportunity to gain insight to the relative strengths and challenges in which the services operate; lessons can be learned from what went well, and the challenges may present opportunities in which services or solutions can be designed and provisioned in order to fill the identified gaps. Caution is advised when attempting to apply one statement made by a particular demonstrator operating in a specific scientific domain as representative of the requirements or opinion of the whole segment, or even of the whole community. However, the experiences of the Science Demonstrators provide practical insight that can be part of the process of informing the potential services that could make up the EOsc Service Portfolio. The extracted requirements (functional and non-functional) and identified gaps help us to understand more about where demand for specific value-added services lie in the area of contributing to the European Open Science Cloud’s mission. It should be noted that the project has been defined by investing primarily in manpower and access to existing infrastructure, rather than investing in middleware and other infrastructure service components necessary for integrating services. Furthermore, it may have been difficult for the science demonstrators to justify (re)designing their services for the purposes of EOscpilot, without there being a more long-term maintained infrastructure for testing and integration activities.

This chapter draws on the findings, feedback, lessons learned, and recommendations explored under D4.4 and, in combination with chapter 3 herein, looks to identify the types of services to be proposed as candidates for the service portfolio roadmap.

4.2. Science Demonstrators services requirements

Chapter 5 of D4.4 captures the outcomes described by the Science Demonstrators final reports under four topics: ‘Technical Challenges and Functional Requirements’ (under which it further explored ‘Services’ and ‘Resources’), ‘Policy Challenges and Governance Challenges and Non-Functional Requirements’, ‘Cultural Challenges’ and ‘FAIR Principles and Open Science’. Section 5.1.1 makes particular references to EOsc Services. This deliverable D5.5 has also utilised and distilled salient information from the final reports in order to further illustrate the gaps in service provision that could be fulfilled via the EOsc service portfolio in the future (refer to Annex B for further details). It is important to note that the ‘service requirements’ identified during the Science Demonstrators are more in the style of high-level functional requirements, and do not necessarily translate directly to specific services.

The services required by the Science Demonstrators can be grouped into the following themes: automation, integration and orchestration (based on modular services); computation and storage; training, support and standardisation; access/authentication/single sign-on tools and policies; metadata policies and services.

³³ <https://eosc-pilot.eu/content/d44-consolidated-science-demonstrator-evaluation-report>

4.2.1. Automation, integration and orchestration

The demonstrators were generally prepared and orchestrated manually (i.e. cloud environments, infrastructure, etc., all configured/deployed separately, and manually connected to cross-infrastructure analysis tool sets), and ad hoc solutions were created to meet requirements for services to interoperate across infrastructures. This approach identified that automated service orchestration across organisational and infrastructural boundaries would add real value to the researchers, especially where services are modular. The commentary supports the position that the global orchestration of e-infrastructures on the hardware level (e.g., network + storage + compute + access + sharing) in a distributed way is the new challenge for many projects, and is an area in which the EOOSC could be of service. The technical design and feasibility for such orchestration would need to be carried out as a specific activity, and such orchestration may potentially be supported by use of modular components deployed using containerised approaches, or by EOOSC-supplied ‘shepherds, architects or service enablers’ who design and implement the cross-infrastructure resources in response to specific and specialist requirements.

4.2.2. Computation and storage

Many services are already available to researchers via various R&E and commercial channels; however, to date they have been offered in various ‘vertical’ solutions, and at a level where specific technical expertise is required in order to leverage their full potential. It is vital that such services are capable of operating at very large scales, without the need to negotiate additional resources, and that the solutions can be operated by researchers without IT backgrounds. Some Science Demonstrators called for enhanced support to EOOSC System Users, as well as investment in high-performance shared network storage and object-storage solutions, which is a high priority of the European Data Infrastructure and the e-Infrastructure community as a whole, and highlights opportunities to more strongly promote the services already offered in this space. Specifically, long-term trusted data repository service requirements were highlighted by D4.4.

4.2.3. Training, support, engagement & standardization

A common theme running through the Science Demonstrator reports was that improved user support would be appreciated, and improved engagement with the research community (without making assumptions on their behalf as to what would be useful for their research). There is a need for training in terms of both specific and generic/core services. In order to support FAIR principles, there is a demand for:

- Unification and standardisation (e.g. of metadata standards, workflow description standards, for example), where practical and possible, with adapters/converters/translation tools between standards potentially being made available according to specific cross-discipline user group requirements/demand.
- Education and training (on open science policies and best practices).
- FAIR policies to be sympathetic to attribution of early research results.
- Specific ‘professional, consulting and training’ services should be designed and deployed with this in mind. To enable researchers to improve their ability to find and access reusable data, and to make their published data conform to the FAIR principles without additional overhead, with an opportunity to collaborate with the FAIRsFAIR project that *“addresses the development and concrete realization of an overall knowledge infrastructure on academic quality data management, procedures, standards, metrics and related matters based on the FAIR data principles”*³⁴.

This could be delivered via multiple channels, such as, physical and virtual workshops/seminars, in-house training, MOOCs, and interactive video resources. Noteworthy to mention, the EOOSC Portal already has a ‘Training and Support’ services section³⁵, with some services registered and able to cater to some extent the needs mentioned above.

³⁴ <https://www.esfri.eu/sites/default/files/Infrid%20Dillo.pdf>

³⁵ <https://www.eosc-portal.eu/services-resources/training>

4.2.4. Access/authentication/single sign-on tools and policies

This topic was arguably featured the most prominently throughout the final reports of the Science Demonstrators and was also a theme identified during the EOSC Engagement Events. The context is that users expect that AAI will improve the user experience generally, but that it could also further facilitate and enable to ‘service chaining’ that is to be achieved within the EOSC. Therefore, whilst AAI is currently promoted in the EOSC Service Registry, consideration should be given to the manner in which cross-infrastructure resources interact automatically.

4.2.5. Metadata policies and services

Other reports highlighted the concept of high-quality metadata being a good facilitator of access to services and data, and the potential for new services in this area was indicated:

- Public temporary repository of acquisition metadata and image processing workflows.
- Services for validating and enhancing meta data in a transparent procedure and offering options to transparently check consistency with FAIR principles; or intermediary data stewardship services (prior to publication).

4.3. Other generic observations

Some other generic observations were communicated concerning requirements for the EOSC, that do not fit to a particular service category. For example:

- Improved usability of interfaces, and reusability among components, should be a key consideration in design and provision of services; some called for simplified installation and deployment processes of the services currently on offer (using e.g. containerisation).
- Either enabling EOSC services should be sufficiently simple to integrate without support from technical experts, or, an increased number of experts should be made available to assist with integrating enabling services. The ‘shepherds, architects or service enablers’ could provide a valuable service in this context.
- Other demonstrators were restricted by software component licensing constraints (where users must be licensed to use or access specific software, the integrated service must manage a way to check entitlement and to present license usage terms to the user concerned) and security restrictions (where resources intended to be ‘cloudified’ are behind firewalls rather than in demilitarized zones, DMZ, and technically cannot connect to outside services without competent design, specific ports or routes to defined IPs being configured and penetration testing)³⁶. It was recommended that this should be addressed in the design of interoperable and federated services, and consultancy services could be offered in this area to ‘audit’ each service component, prior to publication, to highlight restrictive licences, providing a Red/Amber/Green status for each component.

4.4. Conclusions

Many of the final reports of the science demonstrators echo similar themes and gaps in the fulfilment of requirements. Whilst the themes identified via the EOSC engagement events were also present in the final reports of the science demonstrators, as more practical applications of the available services were experienced during the process of performing the demonstrators, it was presumably possible to therefore take a more technically focused approach in their assessment of the services on offer. A set of high-level requirements and gaps have emerged from the Science Demonstrators, and it would be necessary for EOSC to explore and investigate further, particularly around feasibility for automated orchestration across distributed systems and organisational, geographic and infrastructural boundaries, particularly in terms of further exploring use cases, architectures, AAI policies and technical design. Noteworthy to mention,

³⁶ See Annex B, Photon-Neutron science demonstrator, which describes licensing and security provisioning being a constraint to full-integration of services.

recommendations to bridge these gaps emerged from EOSCpilot WP6 recently ³⁷, *“to support the interoperability of the infrastructure.”*

We conclude this chapter by recommending that the prioritisation of the service needs should be done for each Science Demonstrator. It would certainly help to support and build the EOSC service roadmap.

³⁷ <https://eoscipilot.eu/content/d68-final-eosc-architecture>

5. ROADMAP AND FINAL CONSIDERATIONS

5.1. Service Portfolio Roadmap

The ‘Commission Staff Working Document: Implementation Roadmap for the European Open Science Cloud’³⁸, describes the objective to:

“The Work Programme foresees developing the initial shared resources around the EOsc-hub project, the EOsc Portal and a catalogue of data infrastructures and services. Therefore, the process of federation entails two inter-related activities:

*“1. **To develop shared resources as part of the federating core.** In the initial phase, Horizon 2020 projects, notably the EOsc-hub, will provide an access channel complementing the access mechanisms in use at different data infrastructures. A portfolio of projects described later in this SWD [...] will **provide horizontal services such as a portal, authentication and authorization and security services, allowing users to access the computing, data and services of pan-European and disciplinary research data infrastructures**, which already federate data infrastructures at the European level. **A catalogue of EOsc services, including both thematic and generic services** – for data storage, management and analytics, simulation and visualization, distributed computing, etc. will help researchers to discover, select and use the services they need.*

*2. **To connect to the core a large number of research data infrastructures** (henceforth data infrastructures). The hub would relay the resources and the services of data infrastructures funded at EU, national and regional level. Service and resources might be both generic and thematic-specific. **The progressive federation over time of existing service providers in the EOsc would provide a single, coherent access channel to EOsc services at European level that meets researchers’ needs for data sharing, management and computing. This process of federation of resources would be implemented gradually, based on simple guidelines consistent with existing good practices.**”*

These activities recognize that the gradual evolution of services away from silos and into a federated model is dependent on a number of enabling services that will lead to the eventual federated model. The document later points out that to further develop the architecture, that enables federated data and services, the EOsc will require specific services that enable the researcher in its general working practices, particularly around accessing and reusing existing data, and making their own data FAIR:

*“The consultation and the available evidence show that **EOsc might offer five main types of services for European researchers**. While such services are currently being provided to specific scientific communities, they are limited by the contexts of disciplines, by national boundaries or by both. The EOsc would make them all available irrespective of discipline or national boundaries. These services are: 1. **A unique identification and authentication service and an access point and routing system towards the resources of the EOsc.** 2. **A protected and personalized work environment/space** (e.g. logbook, settings, compliance record and pending issues). 3. **Access to relevant service information** (status of the EOsc, list of federated data infrastructures, policy-related information, description of the compliance framework) and to specific guidelines (how to make data FAIR, to certify a repository or service, to procure joint services). 4. **Services to find, access, re-use and analyze research data generated by others**, accessible through appropriate catalogues of datasets and data services (e.g. analytics, fusion, mining, processing). 5. **Services to make their own data FAIR, to store them and ensure long-term preservation.** ... The projects will deliver the initial catalogue of services and data to be provided by EOsc and will define the delivery model(s) for the services. Those catalogues would be enriched periodically based on the process of federation.*

³⁸ https://ec.europa.eu/research/openscience/pdf/swd_2018_83_f1_staff_working_paper_en.pdf

Drawing from the EOSC Implementation Roadmap document, the EOSCpilot Science Demonstrators, the meetings and the multitude of discussions/contributions with researchers and other knowledgeable people, the outcome can be mapped to a time scale that crucially depends on the level of integration (governance, funding, user access) reached with the (federated) infrastructures. To assist progressive development of EOSC, a user-driven approach to the development of the service portfolio is preferred. This approach has been captured in this chapter and, based on the outcome, it is proposed to partition development of services in three, partly overlapping, phases. In this case, tools and services will become progressively more “FAIR”. The roadmap reflects the outcome of the experiences gathered during the work with the Science Demonstrators, the early adopters of the EOSC Services, and also incorporates the relevant implementation recommendations made by the High-Level Expert Group³⁹.

An approach that builds on a robust foundation of ‘internal’, shared services and gradually builds and improves on that set of services, whilst giving service providers the opportunity to publish outwardly the services it offers to researchers, until it reaches a full-scale set of federated and/or integrated/orchestrated services that can be consumed according to a relevant business model is recommended. Priorities concerning delivery of specific services might be determined according to the size of the market segment or scientific domain concerned or preferred, according to whether the gap has been highlighted many times across multiple scientific domains.

Generally, where a *product* roadmap would capture ‘confirmed’ and ‘candidate’ *features* to be added to a specific service, a *service portfolio* roadmap broadly sets out a target timeline and/or structure for evolving the *type and number of services* offered within a portfolio of services, working within a service portfolio management framework. Therefore, in the context of analysing recommendations for a forward-looking service portfolio, it would be more appropriate to use the term ‘recommended’ instead of ‘candidate’. While the EOSC evolves, more services are expected to be onboarded once they comply with the rules of participation and enter the service catalogue via the SPM routes sketched in Figure 1, and more complex integrated services will eventually be included. In the following Figure 2, the timeline has been broken down into three distinct phases (‘early implementation’, ‘wider deployment’ and ‘achieving maturity’), during which there is both a design (for future services) and implementation (for those that can be feasibly added to the catalogue) elements. The goal is to show the nature of services and their implementation over time within the phases described as follows.

5.1.1. Early implementation

This phase maps to the service management principle of ‘Service Promotion’ described by deliverable 5.3⁴⁰. During this phase, the primary focus would be building on the initial catalogue of services in terms of variety, volume and complexity of services, and where services and service consumption continues to be delivered by the relevant service provider. Stable internal services are built, based on known quality criteria to solidify trust. Only those services that can be acquired through simple business models are offered during this phase. Easy access to data and easy data sharing is enabled through federated services offered with single sign-on umbrella. In the case of external services, those services are discovered via the EOSC catalogue, and all aspects of service management are carried out by the service provider itself. During this phase the design perspective looks toward understanding demand for specific services to D5.3 be made interoperable, federated and/or integrated, the architecture that would support that federation/integration and the identity and authorization systems required to deliver that level of federation and integration.

Noteworthy to mention, the EOSC Portal launch⁴¹ is the first materialization of this phase. Two other prerequisites of this phase are: a) a common service model for describing all recommended services in the catalogue; b) an onboarding process for newcomers to register their services in the catalogue.

³⁹ <https://eosc-pilot.eu/eosc-recommendations-hleg-interim-report>

⁴⁰ <https://eosc-pilot.eu/content/d53-eosc-federated-service-management-framework>

⁴¹ <https://eosc-hub.eu/news/european-open-science-cloud-officially-launched>

Figure 2 - EOsc Service Portfolio roadmap.

5.1.2. Wider deployment phase

During this phase, the ‘service promotion’-level services move into ‘continual service improvement’ processes, and it is considered ‘business as usual’ to add further services (and more service providers) to the service catalogue and to make enhancements to the internal services that support the service catalogue. The principle of ‘Semi-Integrated Service Management’ described by deliverable 5.3 applies. External services are findable through catalogues that provide transparent views on quality, accessibility, usability, accountability and value propositions, and new services would include long-term trusted data repositories. Its primary focus is given to deploying services that improve FAIRness of data, promoting standards that make services interoperable, working with existing providers of well-established platforms to who will integrate/interoperate with EOSC and in improvement of user experience of interoperability between existing services. It should be possible by then to provide ‘chains’ of service components offered by multiple service providers that are brought together by AAI and federated support models, even if they are not fully integrated by this time. Ad hoc automated service orchestration may be designed and used as case studies for further automated orchestration of services to be delivered in the later phase and, until that is available, service components could be manually orchestrated, depending on manpower being made available to do so. The design perspective then looks to the implementation of interoperable services that could be offered via the innovative business models, and that support federated and/or integrated service provision. Such design must recognize the challenge presented by licensing and security constraints, and should recommend a solution (whether technical- or process-led) to flag and prevent accidental breach of 3rd-party licensing restrictions. Support models would need to respond to the recommendations made within deliverable 5.3.

5.1.3. Achieving maturity phase

The principle of ‘fully integrated Service Management’ described by deliverable 5.3 applies here. Recommendations for this phase at the time of writing this deliverable are less defined, and would be informed and solidified by the outcome of the activities in the second phase; however, by this time the service catalogue used for service promotion would be well-established and mature, and there should be a number of simple federated, interoperable service components available for use that would be the subject of continual improvement processes. The primary focus of this stage would be to deploy added value, integrated services, where the EOSC becomes more capable of addressing more complex use cases of federated service components, and designing/implementing additional services with special purpose functionality and community-specific features. New and existing services must, by that time, benefit from improved integration and provide standard interfaces enabling use by multiple communities. It is likely that federation or integration that depends on additional, more complex business models will be addressed during this phase that were not possible to be addressed by the earlier phase.

Throughout each phase, it is recommended that continual improvement principles provide a mechanism for users to communicate any feedback concerning specific services. The feedback is analysed by the service owner and will relay a proposal to the EOSC Governance with a position statement (where funding for development of that service is no longer available) or information regarding any plans to enhance the service in response to user requirement. The user support should always follow the level of maturity of the service portfolio itself. As an example, in the early phase, the service provider is responsible for setting up the process of providing support and handling user requests, service failures, etc. In the wider deployment phase, the support processes should be documented by EOSC based on well-defined SLAs with the provider. When the portfolio reaches maturity phase, all support processes should be documented and recorded, with transparent steps for the user (e.g. ticketing system provided by EOSC).

5.2. High-level recommendations

To conclude this deliverable, we would like to emphasise a number of topics. We consider them as cornerstones that emerged from the work developed by EOSCpilot Task 5.2, and we expect these topics to be pursued by the relevant implementation projects supporting the European Open Science Cloud vision. This deliverable does not attempt to prioritise these observations, and the sequence below does not imply ordering. The recommendations are made for the purposes of the wider implementation to prioritise based

on strategic factors. Services cover both compute services and data services or services that combine both. Since EOOSC is a data driven project a large number of services are related to data, however for the organization and management of the services it is irrelevant if these relate to compute or data.

#1: Service Portfolio Management & Governance

Service Portfolio Management is an ITSM strategic process with high impact for all EOOSC stakeholders. This process ensures that EOOSC is able to cope with the demands and requirements from the customers. As such, we recommend that EOOSC Governance body takes close control/ownership of this process to ensure current and future business plans succeed. Strong service portfolio management and governance would assist the achievement of the European Open Science Cloud vision, especially in the context of bringing together the various thematic service catalogues of the multiple European implementation projects, with the potential to create a coherent and recognisable ‘catalogue of catalogues’, additional to the portfolio of services offering value across all disciplines.

#2: Capabilities and Service Roadmap

A set of desired capabilities and associated services was identified from the EOSCPilot Science Demonstrators (as described herein). These should be addressed by the EOOSC service roadmap to ensure the needs of representative communities are met, with particular emphasis on feasibility and design of automated orchestration between services (across infrastructural and geographic boundaries), which is where the real added value of EOOSC is likely to lie.

#3: Agile Portfolio Management

An agile EOOSC Service Portfolio Management, much like agile project management, values that customers and service providers work more closely. It will ensure that EOOSC offer provides the expected added value in this European competitive Digital Market. Furthermore, the final report and recommendations of the Commission 2nd High-Level Expert Group on the EOOSC – ‘Prompting an EOOSC in practice’⁴², provides “*considerations and pointers for the timely implementation of the EOOSC, based around the concept of a ‘Minimal Viable Product’*”, where a service (a product) should aim to have “*just enough features to satisfy early customers, and to provide feedback for future product development.*” Thus, we recommend that EOOSC services (and notably all core/enabling services) should be managed following agile best practice methodologies, such as the core value concepts highlighted by the Agile Manifesto⁴³.

#4: Reliable EOOSC Services for uptake by service integrators

A resilient set of non-user facing services, i.e. internal EOOSC services, must be federated and or well-integrated, before offering them to the community at large via the EOOSC Service Registry. The development of services, by researchers and service integrators, aiming to integrate service components by EOOSC, need to rely and trust on mature EOOSC services. Service providers can continue publishing existing services while waiting for a mature internal EOOSC services set.

#5: Service development pace is different across service providers

Recognise that the pace of service development will not align across all service providers. Reaching maturity and full integration with EOOSC services, will happen at different speeds, and is dependent on multiple processes not controlled by EOOSC nor its service management system. Researchers prefer reliability over interoperability and must be made aware of service deployment interdependencies.

⁴² <https://publications.europa.eu/en/publication-detail/-/publication/5253a1af-ee10-11e8-b690-01aa75ed71a1>

⁴³ <http://agilemanifesto.org/>

ANNEX A. EOsc ENGAGEMENT EVENTS

A.1. Representation at the events

The sessions at the ENVRI week and ASTERICS-OBELICS workshop were attended exclusively by members of the corresponding community. At the conferences in Lisbon and Vienna, the organized sessions were attended by a mixed audience, from researchers, service providers and others.

Participants were asked to choose the 'label' that best matched their role / function for the specific event they were attending. If undecided, i.e. the attendant could not tell which of his functions were more important, the label 'other' was chosen. The results are shown in the Table 1 below.

Table 1 - Participants per event and primary job role

	ENVRI plus	ASTERICS-OBELICS	DI4R	EOsc SF
User / Researcher	2	6	10	See bellow
Developer	3	3	6	
Service Provider	6	5	12	
Funder	0	0	3	
Other	7	5	5	
TOTAL	19	19	36	

The EOsc Stakeholders Forum (SF) invited panelists represented the following groups:

- Representing communities
 - Text and data mining
 - Life science and Bioinformatics
 - Earth observation satellites (Terradue)
- Representing Resource Providers
 - EUMETSAT
 - Institut Laue-Langevin (ILL)
 - Helmholtz Data Federation (HDF)
 - EMBL (Heidelberg)
 - Elixir

A.2. Questions discussed at the events

A set of questions, fine-tuned to match the expected event audience, were carefully built. The questions main objective was to focus the attention of the participants, on the capabilities / services they would like EOsc to support and to prioritize the expressed needs. The outcome is valuable to address the EOsc roadmap topic.

Table 2 - List of questions addressed in each event

Event	Questions addressed
ENVRIplus	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What services will your research data workflow benefit the most from if made available and supported in EOSC? Please prioritize. 2. Are there bottlenecks in your research data workflow? How can EOSC help solve these? 3. Are there ENVRI based services you prefer to run in the EOSC or are there objections using the EOSC for ENVRI data services?
ASTERICS-OBELICS	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What capability/service would enhance your workflow / service? 2. What services would you like to host in EOSC? 3. Do you think EOSC is a good place to host your service: why/ why not? 4. What role do you see for EOSC other than described in your previous answers? 5. What services will your research data workflow benefit the most from if made available and supported in EOSC? Please prioritize.
DI4R	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What research data do you find difficult to discover today? 2. What capabilities should EOSC provide to support your research workflow? 3. What are the main bottlenecks in your research data workflow? How can EOSC help solve these? 4. What are the top 2 wishes that the EOSC could fulfil over the next year?
EOSC stakeholder forum	<ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. What are the benefits of EOSC for your research project/community and why do you think researchers should engage in EOSC? 2. In your opinion, what is the highest priority for EOSC to deliver to your community? 3. Quality control of the services contributed to the EOSC is important. How can we balance the criteria for service qualification against the need to encourage service providers to contribute to the EOSC? 4. In EOSC you will bridge requests for services with other infrastructures. (i.e. if you run compute jobs that need access to data made available by another service provider). In what respect is connectivity to other infrastructures important to you? How do you envisage working with the concept of payment by EOSC?

ANNEX B. SUMMARY OF THE SCIENCE DEMONSTRATORS REQUIREMENTS

Demonstrator	Extracts of service requirements
Initial Science Demonstrators	
Environmental & Earth Sciences ENVRI⁴⁴ ENVRI Radiative Forcing Integration to enable comparable data access across multiple research communities by working on data integration and harmonised access.	From report dated 2018/09/11 Contains detailed descriptions of technical challenges experienced (and reliance on manual orchestration), and advises recommendations around training on cloud technologies, virtual machines and webinars on managing Docker containers. Also requests improved network connectivity between service providers.
High Energy Physics DPHEP/WLCG⁴⁵ Large-scale, long-term data preservation and re-use of physics data through the deployment of HEP data in the EOSC open to other research communities.	From report dated 2018/01/02 A need for cross-domain services to interoperate, in a way that challenges in lacking domain-specific, tacit knowledge does not hamper progress.
Social Sciences TEXTCROWD⁴⁶ Collaborative semantic enrichment of text-based datasets by developing new software to enable a semantic enrichment of text sources and make it available on the EOSC.	From report dated 2018/01/08 <i>“Improve usability of cloud infrastructures in terms of user interfaces and reusability among components, to simplify and speed up installation and deployment processes.</i> <i>Provide advanced controls to monitor the status of each component and of the infrastructure as a whole.”</i> <i>“Interoperability among components would work more efficiently on a platform that is able to provide facilities supporting a modular approach, for deploying and running on demand the required components and services. D4Science, for instance, provided an interoperable framework already including the GATE engine and the features to use TEXTCROWD together with the OpenNLP and OpenNER web services, thus simplifying the operations of deployment and execution in a controlled environment.”</i>
Life Sciences Pan-Cancer⁴⁷ Pan-Cancer Analyses & Cloud Computing within the EOSC to accelerate genomic analysis on the EOSC and reuse solutions in other areas (e.g. for cardiovascular & neuro-degenerative diseases).	From report dated 2018/07/23 <i>“EOSC infrastructure providers should be prepared to operate at much larger scales than have been demonstrated within the context of the EOSCPilot project.”</i> <i>“[communication] would be vastly improved if a standardized support queue front end was made available to clients where they could review all of their tickets along with assigned priorities and resolution history along with a clear</i>

⁴⁴ <https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/envri-radiative-forcing-integration>

⁴⁵ <https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/high-energy-physics>

⁴⁶ <https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/textcrowd>

⁴⁷ <https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/pan-cancer-analyses-cloud-computing-within-eosc>

	<p><i>and precise definition of the ticket handling Standard Operating Procedures and the SLAs associated with each step and ticket severity”.</i></p> <p><i>“A catalogue of datasets would be beneficial as the inability to move cloud-scale datasets will largely dictate environment choice by scientific groups in the future”.</i></p> <p><i>“the biggest skills gap is related to the additional IT management requirements placed upon the scientific community by operating in the cloud. This includes basic Linux administration, networking, security, and operational management within a distributed computing environment. “</i></p> <p><i>“Standardized [identity and access management] IAM service across providers and services”.</i></p> <p><i>“Standardized storage services – block storage, shared-NFS, object storage.”</i></p>
<p>Physics Photon-neutron⁴⁸</p> <p>The photon-neutron community to improve the community’s computing facilities by creating a virtual platform for all users (e.g., for users with no storage facilities at their home institutes).</p>	<p>From report dated 2018/06/27</p> <p><i>“The practical implementation and scaling of swarms introduces a strong requirement for interoperable registries, and repositories providing trusted services to distribute container solutions. They should apply access and authorization management, user-attribute and role management, thereby keeping track of acknowledged licenses. To guarantee interoperability of such systems, they should be derived from some EOSC standards, AAI, licenses and certificates.”</i></p> <p><i>“Cooperative use of provisioning infrastructures needs a careful balance between security concerns and usability of tools like git, puppet or foreman. The local services are currently secured but not usable in a truly cooperative or federated manner, which make reuse of configuration templates subject to administrative overhead.”</i></p> <p><i>“For interoperable trust between networks and cloud providers, also comparable metrics to control SLAs and QoS are needed”.</i></p> <p><i>“Integration of devtools and knowledge tools to accelerate communication and publish issues, findings and solutions”.</i></p> <p><i>“Networking issues like opening ports, granting access, placing services inside/outside DMZ still have to be addressed. “</i></p>
<p>Additional 5 Science Demonstrators started on July 1, 2017</p>	
<p>Energy Research PROMINENCE⁴⁹</p> <p>HPCaaS for Fusion - Access to HPC class nodes for the Fusion Research community through a cloud interface.</p>	<p>From the final report dated 2018/09/27</p> <p><i>“there are no services in the catalog which have the ability to deploy infrastructure automatically across multiple FedCloud sites.”</i></p> <p><i>“Interoperability between the different AAI infrastructures in different organisations is an important issue that needs to be solved in order to simplify access to both compute and storage resources”.</i></p> <p><i>“Increased and standard interfaces between EOSC core components is currently limited, meaning each user needs to perform their own tailored integration.”</i></p>

⁴⁸ <https://eoscpilot.eu/science-demos/photon-neutron-science-demonstrator>

⁴⁹ <https://eoscpilot.eu/prominence-hpcaas-fusion>

	<p>From the high-level report</p> <p><i>“Currently the core EOSC services used within this project are not sufficiently simple to allow easy integration without support from technical experts; as such the number of experts should be increased to meet expected demand or the interfaces need to be simplified.”</i></p> <p><i>“The lack of a coherent AAI solution is an issue, as is the lack of integration between core services. For example, it should not be required for each EOSC user to do their own integration between EGI FedCloud and B2DROP”</i></p>
<p>Earth Sciences EPOS/VERCE⁵⁰</p> <p>Virtual Earthquake and Computational Earth Science e-science environment in Europe.</p>	<p>From the final report dated 2018/11/08</p> <p><i>“The infrastructures should be more specific and technical about their service offering. While the current service catalogues are already an improvement to the prior absence of documentation, they do not provide much more than high-level abstracts. For some services, there is simply too much choice offered in components (without offering them hosted), without any clear recommendations or evaluations. The infrastructures should focus on stable platform services to a concise set of services and openly communicate this.”</i></p> <p>From the high-level final report</p> <p><i>“Scale-up and multi-architecture support offered by the EOSC computational services. Possibility for expert research-developers to develop serverless workflows, where available resources are allocated and scaled dynamically, removing the burden of configuring specific providers. Such mechanisms should be provided or brokered by the EOSC, who should also advertise to the stakeholders those tools that are compliant with such mechanisms.”</i></p> <p><i>“Computational tools offered by EOSC should be aware of the existence of these service and use them offering possibilities of adaptation to the use-cases (granularity, privacy rules and visibility), and contextualisation to the user’s domain. FAIR principles should take care about attribution and privacy level for preliminary results in order to be incorporated since the early days of a particular research campaign.”</i></p>
<p>Life Sciences / Genome Research Life Sciences Datasets⁵¹</p> <p>Leveraging EOSC to offload updating and standardizing life sciences datasets and to improve studies reproducibility, reusability and interoperability.</p>	<p>From the final high-level report</p> <p><i>“We believe that the implementation of universal standards to describe and store pipelines is an inevitable requirement to foster reproducibility in science. In our opinion, even if current available repositories permit to store and describe pipelines, still some work is needed to easily link data repositories with pipelines ones [...] education and training processes are required to form a new generation of scientists more engaged in adopting open science policies and best practices, such as the use of containers to manage software dependencies, along with the use of a source code management platform and workflow system, like Nextflow, to enable portable and reproducible deployment across different execution platforms”.</i></p>

⁵⁰ <https://eoscpilot.eu/eposverce-virtual-earthquake-and-computational-earth-science-e-science-environment-europe>

⁵¹ <https://eoscpilot.eu/life-science-datasets>

<p>Life Sciences / Structural Biology CryoEM Workflows⁵²</p> <p>Linking distributed data and data analysis resources as workflows in Structural Biology with cryo Electron Microscopy: Interoperability and reuse.</p>	<p>Extract from Final High-Level Report</p> <p><i>“a public repository of acquisition metadata and image processing workflows for new acquisitions, as a temporary repository until the data is finally analyzed and deposited in the standard public databases (EMDB and EMPIAR).”</i></p> <p><i>“It would also be very useful to have an authentication policy such that biologists coming out from an EM facility could continue the image processing in some of the EOsc cloud machines.”</i></p>
<p>Physical Sciences / Astronomy LOFAR Data⁵³</p> <p>Easy access to LOFAR data and knowledge extraction through Open Science Cloud.</p>	<p>From final report dated 2018/11/15</p> <p><i>“[recommend] support for CWL and, in particular container based, preferably Singularity, deployments on all EOsc clusters (including grid/HPC).”</i></p> <p><i>“[recommend] a wide(r) deployment of high capacity network connections between computing centers; on demand point to point connections”.</i></p> <p>Challenges: <i>“Sustainability of services in a collaborative environment: Who takes responsibility for defining, building and supporting community-oriented services. (Infrastructure provider, Expertise center, Research support organization). Each needs acknowledgement and visibility.”</i></p> <p><i>“There is already a large number of services and tools available within the EOsc, often with overlapping functionality – it is a challenge to find and evaluate appropriate service components effectively. For each community to survey the whole landscape and evaluate all options is not practical.</i></p> <p><i>An annotated service/tool catalog including specific strengths and weaknesses, enabling communities/users to provide ‘reviews’ and tips would be a useful help. The surveying could be facilitated through a structured set of demo’s and/or workshops.</i></p> <p><i>Broad support for VM/containers would be extremely useful to deal with application deployment complexity (for LOFAR, but likely for many communities). General purpose support for the CWL standards would be useful as well.</i></p> <p><i>What we are currently missing in our setup are appropriate workflow management and monitoring tools. We aim to look e.g. at Airflow in a future follow-up.</i></p> <p><i>It could be considered to provide a central EOsc linked data platform as a low-threshold entry point for communities that are new to the technology.</i></p> <p><i>Finally, data locality is an issue for Radio Astronomy in particular. We are limited by (network) connectivity between source and destination storage on the one hand and appropriate computational infrastructure on the other hand. This will become a serious issue when expanding our demonstrator to include multiple locations (e.g. FZJ and PSNC for LOFAR).”</i></p>

⁵² <https://eoscpilot.eu/cryoem>

⁵³ <https://eoscpilot.eu/lofar-data>

	<p>“Scientific service enablers need to learn the new language for describing workflows. The tutorials are good, but a workshop for CWL programming would be beneficial.</p> <p>Users need to gain skills in developing pipelines in an abstract way. There needs to be more awareness that thinking about pipelines in an abstract way makes it easier to deploy on large scale.</p> <p>End users know little about containers, VM’s & CWL. Training needed.</p> <p>Service enablers need to identify the most appropriate or generic solution(s). it is not always clear which infrastructure/service will be the best fit or is most easily adapted for a specific purpose. Information and training needed.”</p> <p>“Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Support for containerized software deployment • IO/throughput performance • CWL Workflow execution and monitoring (for End Users and Service Enabling organizations) • Move away from user owned X509 certificates” <p>“Non-functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Scalability (IO & data volume) • Usability of (grid) infrastructure • User and Service Enabler support by infrastructure providers”
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Additional 5 Science Demonstrators started on December 1, 2017

<p>Generic Technology Frictionless Data Exchange⁵⁴</p> <p>Frictionless Data Exchange Across Research Data, Software and Scientific Paper Repository.</p>	<p>Date of report unknown</p> <p>Suggested the following:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • New, scalable protocols • Training on ResourceSync and associated tools • Specifying use of ResourceSync as a policy statement • “most of the data hosted in the EOsc services should have a metadata definition that could be shared to enable an easier distribution and discoverability” • “a distributed/federated infrastructure where all the components should easily communicate “
<p>Life Sciences – Genome Research Bioimaging⁵⁵</p> <p>Mining a large image repository to extract new biological knowledge about human gene function.</p>	<p>From pre-final report dated 2018/11</p> <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Object storage access for computation in a cluster of vCPUs with shared high-performance file system.” <p>Non-functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • “Non-expert user-friendly tenancy set-up” (Cloud environment) • software deployment

⁵⁴ <https://eoscpilot.eu/frictionless-data-exchange-across-research-data-software-and-scientific-paper-repositories>

⁵⁵ <https://eoscpilot.eu/life-sciences-%E2%80%93-genome-research-bioimaging-mining-large-image-repository-extract-new-biological>

<p>Astro Sciences VisIVO⁵⁶</p> <p>Data Knowledge Visual Analytics Framework for Astrophysics.</p>	<p>From report dated 2018/11/07</p> <p>Functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • integrate visual analytics services; • increase the access of computing resources for analysis; • provide services for a federated and interoperable virtual environment enabling collaboration and re-use of data and knowledge; • optimization of the archiving of complex data (and meta-data) such as the multi-wavelength surveys under FAIR principles. <p>Non-functional requirements:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Usability, enhance usability for end users • Accessibility and Integrability to facilitate the integration of new components coming from the scientific community within the EOsc • Documentation • Failure management, to help also debugging failing computations.
<p>Earth Sciences Hydrology⁵⁷</p> <p>Switching on the EOsc for Reproducible Computational Hydrology by FAIRifying eWaterCycle and SWITCH-ON.</p>	<p>From report dated 2018/11/29</p> <p>FAIRness (or lack thereof) of data was a recurring issue, broadly due to a lack of ‘authoritative metadata’ or restrictive licenses.</p> <p>‘Higher level’ services are required, with features such as email-based invite systems and web-client based applications (rather than fat clients that require installation).</p> <p>Specific services identified as a requirement were:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • File sharing (Dropbox for large data sets) • Execution services for standards-based workflows • Authentication and Authorization services • Persistent storage (with identifiers like DOIs) <p>‘Dataset providers’ should be obliged to create FAIR versions of each dataset, rather than the individual researchers being expected to do it themselves.</p>
<p>Social Sciences and Humanities VisualMedia⁵⁸</p> <p>A service for sharing and visualizing visual media files on the web.</p>	<p>From report dated 2018/11/07</p> <p>“Supporting and enhancing the availability of FAIR data is a key issue in many scientific domains. The Visual Media Service tries to propose a solution to some key issues: how to manage the multiplicity of visual data types, the many visualization applications available/needed for each data type, the complexity of publishing those data on the web to allow easier sharing between experts.”</p> <p>“The main political challenge in the Cultural Heritage domain is to convince potential users of the added value of uploading visual media results and to make</p>

⁵⁶ <https://eoscpilot.eu/astro-sciences-visivo-data-knowledge-visual-analytics-framework-astrophysics>

⁵⁷ <https://eoscpilot.eu/earth-sciences-%E2%80%93-hydrology-switching-eosc-reproducible-computational-hydrology-fairifying>

⁵⁸ <https://eoscpilot.eu/social-sciences-and-humanities-visualmedia-service-sharing-and-visualizing-visual-media-files-web>

*them available to the community on the web ... **many people in this community are still very protective with the data they produce** or are working with.”*

*“We **need some incentive to foster data sharing** (for example, considering quantity and quality of data shared as one of the items evaluated in a CV in promotion or hiring processes”*

“The offer of standard e-infrastructures is often too much oriented to ICT developers (offering basic technologies). If we consider the specific Cultural Heritage domain/community, then most of the potential users are looking for ready to use solutions/tools rather than libraries to be used for SW development.”

“Development of standardized policies around data sharing. Development of standardized policies to visualize and analyze visual data. Stability in time of the resources shared by the infrastructure.”

ANNEX C. GLOSSARY

Term	Explanation
AAI	Authentication and Authorization Infrastructure
EC	European Commission
ESFRI	European Strategy Forum on Research Infrastructures
ITSM	Information Technology Service Management
OLA	Operational Level Agreement
PID	Persistent Identifier
RI	Research Infrastructure
SLA	Service Level Agreement
SLM	Service Level Management
SMS	Service Management System
SPM	Service Portfolio Management
TRL	Technology Readiness Levels